

Contemporary West African Vodun

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Entry tags: ancestor veneration, Animist, African Religions, Religious Group

The word Vodun means spirit in Fon and Ewe, two languages spoken in coastal Benin, Togo, and South East of Ghana. The Vodun religion is an ancestral religion common to the population living in the west African coastal corridor covering the countries mentioned above. The deities comprise of the supreme god and intermediary gods who cover different domain of life. The supreme god is known as 'Mawu', a benevolent god who has the control of the whole universe. The Vodun religion in its encounter with imported religions was associated to a demonic religion and continues to lose membership due to the westernization of the region. The contemporary Vodun religion evolves in an environment where most members practice syncretism with Islam and Christianity and most members are secretive in their allegiance to the Vodun gods. For contemporary Vodun worshippers, the supreme god Mawu is most of the time assimilated to a monotheist god. Depending on the tribe, Mawu is either a female or a male or both. Mawu plays a moderator role in that all the intermediary gods' actions are controlled. Below Mawu, there are seven intermediary divinities. These intermediary gods are active in everyday life and play a role in their domain. Sakpata is the god of the Earth. Hêbioso is the thunder god. Agbe is known as the god of the sea. Gû represents the god of war. Agê is in the domain of agriculture. Finally, Lêgba is the unpredictable god and serves as the contact point with the other gods. The ambivalence of modern worshippers is mostly visible in the rituals and sacrifices made to these gods in order to change the course of life in the changed world. Though some of Vodun priests can be found in the inner cities, the majority are located in rural area reinforcing the mystery and secrecy that surround them and their practitioners. Blood sacrifices, incantations, rituals, and the confinement of children and women in Vodun convents are some of the practices of this religion. Contemporary Vodun practitioners have adapted their religion to their time. With the introduction of monotheist religions, Vodun was predicted to disappear. Instead, Vodun continues to survive and has expanded to the diaspora where the Vodun has become an identity issue for former African slaves' descendants in the Caribbean islands and the Americas. Even in contemporary West Africa, Vodun is used to affirm the African identity of its members in comparison to African Muslims and Christians.

Date Range: 1960 BCE - 2022 CE

Region: Coastal West Africa

Region tags: Africa, Central Africa, Eastern Africa, Western Africa, Southern Africa, Middle Africa

This region is the coastal area of West Africa that lies between the south West of Nigeria and South East of Ghana.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 2: Blier, Suzanne Preston. 1995. *African Vodun: Art, Psychology, and Power*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Source 3: Mbiti, John. 1975 & 1991. *Introduction to African Religion*. Ibadan & Nairobi: Heinemann Books.

– Source 1: Rush, Dana, 1966 in coastal Bénin : unfinished, open-ended, global / Dana Rush. Nashville : Vanderbilt University Press

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://www.wikiwand.com/en/West_African_Vodun

– Source 1 Description: West African Vodun

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.humanreligions.info/voodoo.html>

– Source 2 Description: An Introduction to Vodun or Voodoo

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.pri.org/stories/2018-05-21/vodun-children-togo-must-dedicate-their-lives-convent>

– Source 3 Description: Vodun children in Togo must dedicate their lives to the convent

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6wNOgBOEF0U>

– Source 1 Description: Vodun Ceremony

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.dloc.com/AA00007884/00001>

– Source 1 Description: The Vodou Archive : Curating and sharing the sources of Vodou religion and culture

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Vodun worshipers are in close contact with Muslims and Christians. Current Christians and Muslims or their forefathers are former practitioners of the Vodun. This explains the existing syncretism that is seen in the region.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is highly competitive. Each religions try to convert the members of other religions. So far, Christianity and especially Pentecostalism is the one attracting more members.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The cultural contact is both accommodating and pluralistic. The notable trait of this contact is its non violent nature. Though each religion tries to show its superiority, there is

conviviality among the members.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: It is not neutral because each religious is trying to acquire members from the other religious group.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: So far, there is no violence. However, the brewing Islamic terrorism in the Sahel is threatening to move to the West Africa coastal region. Notably, about three years ago, an Islamic terrorist group struck the coastal population in the adjacent coastal Cote-d'Ivoire with tens of dead and wounded.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: Indeed, as I mentioned above Islamic groups in the Sahel region are threatening to move towards the coast. The peaceful relation between the religious groups has been strained by the inland violence but has not exploded into opened violence.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: Initiation ceremonies are organized to admit members to the religion. These are both public and secret events. Depending on what the ceremony is it might be public and members of the initiated family members and the public are invited. However the secret part is hidden to the public. These are on going processes until the person reaches the highest level in the priesthood hierarchy.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: In rare occasions where a child who was born because of the intervention of Vodun gods, the parents promise to give the child back to the shrine for the child to serve for a limited number of years or for life. It is not surprising to see children as younger as three years old serving the Vodun gods during a convent visit.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Some people, most of the time women, choose to voluntarily serve in Vodun shrine. In other situation, a family member is single out to serve as a way to pay back Vodun gods who

have done good to the family.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Notes: Most Vodun priests are older people. In West African world view, older age is generally attributed to wisdom and Vodun priests are venerated for that.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: Women play prominent role in Vodun priesthood. In the majority of tribes, women are high priests.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: All members of the group have go through rituals of initiation when they reach a certain age. These rituals are mandatory. There are also special rituals dedicated to particular events such as birth rituals, adolescent rituals, boyhood rituals, and female rituals to cite few.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Spiritual contract

Notes: Community members whether they belong to Fon or Ewe tribes or outside tribes might choose to enter into contract with a particular spirit to achieve a particular success in their life. These contracts can be generated for life and require regular sacrifices to maintain the link.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Vodun religion does not engage in active proselytism. Life issues tend to lead people to join the group. Due to the European colonial demonization, Vodun religion is looked down on.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Vodun religion is officially recognized on the same level as Islam and Christianity. Political involvement is observed during electoral season due to the influence of Vodun priests in their communities.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of apostasy is in Vodun religion. Nowadays, many leave the religion to join either Islam or Christianity. In precolonial era, apostasy was a crime and the person committing it was excluded from the community. Nowadays, it does not come with any punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Notes: Apostates are looked at as outcast or lost person but hardly excluded from the community. The punishment in the contemporary context is that the individual is excluded from participating in any Vodun ceremony.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1400 BCE - 2020 CE

Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– No

Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– No

Notes: Unless the apostate is converted to Islam or Christianity, it is assumed that the apostate will receive a divine punishment. The claim goes that the God of Islam or the God of Christians protect against such punishment.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 7000000

Notes: The breakdown of the estimated population can be found in the demographic section at: https://www.wikiwand.com/en/West_African_Vodun

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 5

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are recognized leaders at the local levels. However, there is no centralized leadership.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: There is an implicit leadership hierarchy depending on the leader's power. The power is derived from the level of knowledge of Vodun spirituality.

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: Due to colonialism, there is no centralized Vodun leadership. The creation of modern states such as Nigeria, Benin, Togo, and Ghana divided the community and led to a decentralized leadership.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

Notes: There are more collegial leadership than centralized leadership.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: The leadership is rather a decentralized leadership due to European colonialism which completely divided the Fon and Ewe tribes between Benin, Togo, and Ghana. The consequence is that there is no known a general overseer of Vodun religion.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: It is more of a collegial leadership that oversees the leaders in the sample region. This is due to the division imposed by colonial boundaries.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 5

Notes: This figure is an estimate. The formation of post colonial states led to a break up into small groups which are independent.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: The conception of Vodun is based on supernatural powers and the leaders are assumed to possess them. There is mystery surrounding these powers and this leads to leaders who are both feared and venerated.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

Notes: These powers are assumed to be transmitted from generation to generations. Ancestors are believed to transmit these powers to their descendants

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– No

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: Generational transmission is assumed because in most of the tribe the same family carries the work of the priesthood.

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: In some circumstances, it is believed that ordinary people can acquire power from a priest. This is done through ceremonies and rituals

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Yes

Notes: Power is associated with priesthood. Only the priests can transmit power to ordinary people. In some of the tribes, the chief is simultaneously the high priest.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the tribes, either it is transmitted from generation to generation in the same family or due to post colonial political interventions, they are chosen. European colonization had a serious impact on tribal customs and practices.

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on small communities within the large community, a leader chooses his own replacement.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

Notes: In some small communities within the large community, a leader's ministers choose the new leader.

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on some community, the religious group chooses its leader. Political intervention interferes with some of these customs.

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

Notes: In recent years, politicians have interfered in choosing some of the communities' leaders completely reshaping the customs of most communities in the region.

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the smaller communities choose this process to elect their leader.

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: Nowadays, the process appears to be corrupted due to political interference. However, it is admitted that the communication with supernatural power is believed to be part of the selection process.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

Notes: Because of the supposed supernatural powers that they have, they are considered infallible.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Followers do not question religious leaders' pronouncements because they are assumed to have supernatural power they can use to harm people. They are more feared than venerated.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

– Yes

Notes: Vodun religion is transmitted from generation to generation through oral tradition. Most of the transmission is done through secret societies and there are no known written scriptures.

↳ Are they written:

– No

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

Notes: Because it is an oral scripture, there is an assumption that it has been altered through the transmission from generation to generation.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: However, the generational transmission assured the interpretation of the scripture through secret societies.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Most of time these select groups are are secret societies.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the Vodun monuments are represented by sacred forest, sacred rivers, idols, and convents. They are diverse and tribally recognizable. Most of the monuments are idols or natural elements. (<https://barefoot-backpacker.com/introduction-to-voodoo-in-west-africa/>)

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 1

Notes: The 1% is an estimate of the percentage area taken up by religious group in each tribe. Due to urbanization, these spaces are continuing to shrink and ceding its population to the other religions.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 3

Notes: The three square meters are also an estimate. These monuments are build on small surface areas usually at the entrance of a village or in homes.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 7

Notes: The seven meters are an estimate because some the tallest idols measure up to ten meters. The size is relative to the importance of the idol.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 2

Notes: Most of the monuments are idols. Their sizes vary from few centimetres to about seven meters. <https://www.flickr.com/photos/ulrichmunsternmann/with/27678089048/>

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 4

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 3

Notes: This figure is an estimate of the cumulative space (public spaces and homes) occupy by religious monuments in one of the largest settlement. The monuments are mostly idols.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Royals and priests tombs are identifiably decorated to highlight their relevance in the community. Visits are organized to see those tombs.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: Temples are the most visible monuments in West African Vodun environment. Most of them are seen at the entrance of a village.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Markets

Notes: The fetish market of Akodessewa in Lome, Togo: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HWbdfNrGPOY> The fetish market is one of the emblematic monument visited by thousands of tourists every year.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

– All public spaces

Notes: Talismans are present on people. At home there are family shrines. In public spaces, usually an idol is erected at the entrance of a village. Usually Vodun nuns and priest are identified by the jewel and the clothe color worn.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Notes: Some disciples are identified with colors worn in their faces. For the specialists, the colors allow them to identify the tribal origin of the adherent.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Snakes are considered as gods and are seen in many shrines.
<https://www.atlasobscura.com/places/the-temple-of-pythons-ouidah-benin>

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: The Sakpata spirit is the earth spirit.

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Most of the idols have human characteristics like speaking, hearing.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Notes: For instance, Hebieso the spirit of thunder is considered as supernatural being.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Ancestors are never considered dead. Their spirits are believed to be alive and protecting the community. There is a continuity between this life and the afterlife.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: Idols are erected representing the different gods.

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: In humans, the dressing code clearly indicates the person's affiliation to the Vodun religion. Amulets, talismans, necklaces, wristbands, white or black clothes are worn to differentiate from the rest of the populations.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Notes: The preponderance of children and women in Vodun convents is remarkable.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: This video shows both the Vodun market and the sacred forest of Amoutive in Lome, Togo:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SABkXp-mZJO>

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Forests, rivers, mountains are considered as sacred and their preservation are very important for the population. For instance in some sacred forests is forbidden to cut trees or to even them for any reason. Only authorized people are allowed in.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: One of the well Vodun pilgrimage is organized in Ouidah in Benin every year on January 10. Adherent come from the neighboring countries and from the diaspora from countries such as United States, Brazil, Cuba, and the Caribbean islands. <https://widerimage.reuters.com/story/voodoo-festival-of-benin>

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for some

Notes: Pilgrimage is mandatory for the societal elite and former convent members than to the general population.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: There is indeed the distinction spirit and body. For instance, it is believed that ancestors never die. The belief insists that even after the decay of the body ancestors are continuing to live among the population. Ceremonies are organized to summon a deceased spirit. The same sacrifices can be performed for a living person's spirit to appease evil spirit that are disturbing that person.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of Vodun religion is centered around spirits. the spirits dominate every aspects of life. The power conferred to the spirit-mind is higher than that of human body and is generally accepted the spirits control the living world including human physical body.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The distinction between visible and invisible worlds is at the center of Vodun pneumatology. The immateriality of the spirit-mind is linked to the invisible world and the material physical body is linked to the visible world.

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: There is an afterlife in the Vodun religion. The afterlife constitutes the invisible world where dead ancestors live. Death itself is seen as a travel to the invisible world. For the believers of Vodun generally accept that the visible and the invisible worlds cohabit and ancestors living in the afterlife world greatly influence the visible world.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: the spatial location of the afterlife is the invisible world which cohabits with the visible world. Because of this worldview, ancestors are never dead and are still here among the living.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– No

Notes: Death is compared to a journey between the visible and the invisible worlds. The afterlife is assimilated to the invisible world.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Afterlife is known as 'Djipo', which means above and is assimilated to the invisible world. This ambivalence of the afterlife is seen in the conception ancestors who are both in the above and live among the population.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: the invisible space

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of reincarnation in Vodun religion is completely different from the known Asian religion's reincarnation. For the Vodun religion, children who resemble some of their ancestors are believed to be the reincarnation of these ancestors.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: The resemblance of children to their dead ancestors constitute reincarnation in Vodun world.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Burial is the only treatment of adherents' corpses due to the belief that death is a voyage to another life. For this reason, it is important to preserve the body intact until the burial to avoid any torment for the dead in the afterlife world.

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

- ↳ Corpse is interred some other way:
 - Yes [specify]: Corpse is interred intact.

- ↳ Cannibalism:
 - No

- ↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):
 - No

- ↳ Feeding to animals:
 - No

- ↳ Secondary burial:
 - No

- ↳ Re-treatment of corpse:
 - No

- ↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
 - No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: If a deceased is a victim of violent death, sacrifices are always performed before the burial. In some instances, if it is a suspected murder, the deceased is asked to exercise revenge and buried with some weapons.

- ↳ Human sacrifices present:
 - No

Notes: There are suspicion of human sacrifices after the death of chief priest or a king but no proof has never been brought to bear.

- ↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:
 - Yes

Notes: If a person died by a violent death like car accident, animal sacrifices are made to appease the spirits. Sacrifices are also performed if the person is suspected to have been murdered.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: The higher is the person in the social hierarchy, grave goods are present to honor the deceased. Ordinary people also do the same to honor their deceased.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: Personal effect usually accompany people on the top of social hierarchy like high priest, kings, and nobles. Most of the time the deceased's casket is secretly closed before the burial to avoid anyone looking inside.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Valuable items are suspected to be buried with high rank dignitaries. Often, tombs are desecrated because of these suspicions.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Depending on the importance of the person's rank in the community.

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: It is usually for the most important families in the communities.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Notes: In rare situation, people are buried in their homes to honor them. It is usually highly ranked family member who are honored in this manner.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is Mawu. He has control over the visible and invisible world. He also control the intermediary gods.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The majority of the tribes in the region assimilates the supreme god to a female with a caring character. He most cases is assumed to have two children the moon and the sun, giving the supreme god a human character.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme god 'Mawu' is assumed to have the characteristics of the sun and the moon respectively male and female which are viewed in some of the tribes as the supreme god's children.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: In some of the communities in the region but not all of them, the monarch is the representative of 'Mawu' on earth.

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Yes [specify]: ancestors
 - Notes: Ancestors are very important for Vodun followers. These ancestors serve as a link between human world and the spirit world.
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Mawu is a benevolent god. Mawu always intervenes to make life better. This is not the case with some of the intermediary gods who can intervene to punish.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Sustainer, provider, caring
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The supreme high god can see whatever is happening the invisible world.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Because of the existence of intermediary gods, the supreme god intervenes indirectly. In some rare cases the supreme god is assumed to intervene to do good by changing the negative intervention of a lesser god.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, when the supreme god is happy, farmers obtain good crop but when the supreme god is not happy the crop is generally bad.

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: motherhood
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - Notes: This is an interesting academic research document about trance possession in Togo: <https://www.upress.virginia.edu/title/2273> This video shows a trance possession: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jLdXJ65DZrI>
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - Notes: A typical Vodun divination is performed this way: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yZpqdICyqUM>
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through the intermediary gods.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: The spirits of the ancestors are believed to be present since the beginning of time.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: There are claims people seeing dead people.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: There are also claims spirits can be felt.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: This is mostly concerned with the spirits of the ancestors who have knowledge of the world.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: This is seen when people are punish of wrong doing. It is generally accepted that a murdered person's spirit can be sent to the murderer to revenge himself.

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: Predict the future

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit of ancestors are very protective. They are called through incantation to intervene. In some situation, they are called upon because they are not happy and offered blood sacrifices to change the situation.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Spirit possession

Notes: Spirits are assumed to take control of human beings and speak through them. Spirit possession can happen during festivals, ceremonies, or unexpectedly.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: Depending on few of the communities in the region, human spirits can only communicate through the monarch.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: nature

Notes: Vodun religion assumes that human spirits can communicate through water, trees, and rocks. Sacrifices are performed to these elements of nature to affect the course of life.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- Notes: The vodun gods are preventive and reactive gods.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Usually people go to the vodun priest who in turn consult the gods who reveal people's personal essence.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: By consulting the vodun priest who is the intermediary, people claim to find about their future.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Claim of knowledge about nature

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: People can be punished by the gods up to death.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: For instance, they claim to provoke rain to come down.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They claim gods' anger can provoke food abundance for instance.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: They claim gods' anger can provoke famine for instance.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: fecundity

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is generally assimilated to a human being mostly as a woman in the majority of the tribes.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Through ancestral practices and Vodun worshipping, followers of Vodun appear to believe that the gods have the power to see everything and monitor everything. The belief goes as far as claiming that the gods guard their communities against evil doer and protect them against everything.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: One of the most important features of the Ewe and Fon people is the community life. The community is more important than the individual. For this reason adherence to social, ethical, and moral norms are the cornerstone of this community life. Not honoring contracts and oaths can lead to deadly consequences. Hospitality is the duty of each and everyone.

However, the introduction of western capitalism is changing these community mores as more people are espousing western individualism.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Because of the tribal diversity of this population, there are many taboos. But the most important one relates to the tribe's totem.

↳ Food:

– Yes

Notes: Food taboo is often related to the settlement and ancestral history of each tribe.

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Notes: Ordinary people are forbidden to visit sacred forest for instance.

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: Only consecrated people like priest are allowed to touch sacred objects.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: sexual activities

Notes: Sexual activities for a number of days are forbidden for priests and people getting near a shrine or a temple or an idol before they join any events involving Vodun worshiping.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Murder is a punishable crime in Vodunland. Gods are involved in to find and punish the criminal.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Murdering a member of other religion is punishable and the gods are involved in the punishment.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Murder of any human being is and the gods are involved in finding and punishing the alleged criminal.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: Adultery is punishable and the gods are involved in through incantations to find proof of culpability.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: Incest is strictly forbidden and gods are assumed to punish those who commit this even if no one knows

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: fornication

Notes: It is a punishable crime by the gods.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Gods resent lying and people committing this act are assume to be punished by them.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: Not honoring oaths is one the most serious moral issue in West African Vodou religion. Some of the consequences are family generational curse leading up to death.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Notes: Laziness is more of social issue than spiritual. In most tribes in the region, lazy people are generally considered as outcast. No family will want their siblings to mary such people.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery is part of the Vodun system. Depending on the person, they might be suspected of having a negative or positive power.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Elders are venerated in West African Vodun. They are considered as the holders of ancestral customs and values including a good knowledge of the Vodun divinities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Gossiping are punishable by the gods especially gossiping concerning the secrets of the gods.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Property crime is punishable and gods are generally called upon to find the person in case that person is unknown.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are seriously concerned about the proper ritual observance. It is generally understood that erroneous ritual observance can lead to serious consequences including death.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Performance of rituals are important to supernatural beings because the rituals are the means of communication with the invisible world where these supernatural beings supposed to be dwelling.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Non-religionists conversion are most of the time transnational. In most cases in contemporary Africa, conversion is done because the person converting wants something from the gods. Because of the transnational nature of these conversions, the supernatural beings are believed to be very pointy about the conversions. It is assumed that if the converts do not honor their side of the contract, serious consequences including death can follow.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Societal norm requires fairness in every aspects of life. Further the supernatural beings care about fairness because of the needed social justice involved in the communal life of the Vodun communities.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Notes: For some of the rituals, members are asked to avoid personal hygiene for number of days which will confer them some power. Hygiene is not a preoccupation of Vodun religion. Dead animals can lay besides idols for many days and pollute the atmosphere with rotten smell. Spoiled food sacrifices and animals are also seen in the middle of crossroads and become smelly for many days.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: tradition

Notes: The tradition is the backbone of Vodun religion. Customs and values are transmitted from generation to generation and the traditional knowledge accumulated through years of practice constitute the knowledge source for the community as a whole and the Vodun priests.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings mete out punishment. The most notable god which is in charge of punishment is is Hebieso, the thunder god who punishes any type of crime including lying, stealing, and even murder.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Most the time the non confessed crimes are believed to be punished by the god. According to the protocol, the priest consults the gods about the crime and ask them and ask them to find the culprit. Generally, any person struck by the thunder is assumed to be the criminal.

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: By consulting the gods, the judgement is triggered and and the culprit is punished through natural element like the thunder-god.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The king or the priest can intervene through the gods in every day life to reward

or punish

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Usually the reason for the supernatural punishment are known and a committed crime or generational fault.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Only in transnational cases where the gods are claiming their for helping a person get pregnant and not fulfilling their side of the contract.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, the gods punish as an example for the members of the community not to repeat the same act.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: When a person's fortunes are terrible, it is generally assumed that their ancestors have done something terrible in the past and they are paying the price.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: An individual's plight is believed to be linked to the deeds of their ancestors. Ceremonies have to be performed to help the person avoid the consequences of their ancestors' deeds.

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– No
Notes: Any happenings has an explanation. Any death, for instance, has to be explained and the causes exposed. Any event does not just happen and the gods always provide an explanation.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– No
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes
Notes: Crop failure always has an explanation, as everything has in this community. Either it is ancestral past deeds or current generation lack of proper veneration of the gods. Bad weather itself appears to have an explanation link to the gods not happy.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes
Notes: Disaster on journeys linked to whether the gods are happy or angry against a person.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes
Notes: Definitely, sickness always has an explanation linked to generational deeds or individual deeds. In this case always important to consult the Vodun priest.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes
Notes: Impaired reproduction especially for women are negatively viewed and can easily lead to ostracism. Accusation of sorcery is often levied against such women.
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: It is known as generational curse in the region.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Gods always reward good deeds. As a consequence, good deeds are very much encouraged. However, in some, it is also assumed that good deeds attract witches who can attack the person doing good to the community. Saying such a good person never live longer is most of the time heard.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: good deed and good ancestry are always rewarded. In some extreme occasion, luck is recognized as the source of reward. Everything has an explanation that is provided by the gods

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Depending on some cases.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: Mostly in cases of generational curses or bad destiny.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

Notes: Because of the simultaneity of visible and the invisible worlds, death is conceived as a travel between the two worlds. Rewards are seen in the lives of descendants.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Good deed by ancestors and their descendants are reflected in the lives of the subsequent generations. Supernatural rewards are then bestowed in this lifetime.

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: Because death is conceived as a journey, there is no end of time or a final judgement but a continuity of life from the visible world to the invisible world.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: These general social norms are ancestral practices transmitted from generations to generations. These norms are generally linked to the Vodun religion and viewed as gods' prescriptions. The Sayings go as if you don't do this, the gods will or not be happy about you or the gods will punish or reward you.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The line is blurred between conventional norms and moral norms due to the oral transmission of religious values from generations to generations. It is difficult to differentiate superstition and social norms from theological precepts and rules. More emphasis is put on what the priests profess as theological precepts and these precepts change from one tribe to the other. The seeming syncretism with imported religions such as Islam and Christianity made this distinction more problematic because of the non-negligible exchanges of moral and conventional values between both sides.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: They are present but are not emphasized because of the notable influence of imported religions to the region. In addition, the demonization of the religion during colonialism, created an environment where most of the theological precepts and norms are viewed as superstition.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Moral norms are norms transmitted through previous generations' practices. They are not specifically prescribed but learned through observation and practices.

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Notes: Moral norms, even if they are not reinforced due to the primacy of modern state's legal institutions, apply to all individuals within the society. These moral norms are transmitted orally from generation to generations and contribute to keeping peace in the communities.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Decency and caring for others are the central virtues that are advocated in addition to the values shown below.

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Even though it is disappearing, individualism is viewed negatively and the community life is viewed as ideal leading to generosity and charity. It is difficult to find a homeless person in these community. Caring for others leads to sharing the little one has with others

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are one of the most important religious practices in the Vodun communities. There are ritual for everything and the concept of purity carries its importance in that it is needed to approach the gods.

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Notes: Familial obedience is also important. With it a person can be excluded from his family. Family exclusions are happening more and more due to conversion to other religions. The most vivid example is that a family refuses to bury a sibling because of disobedience.

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes

Notes: Wisdom in this religion is associated to older age. For this reason, it is surprising that most priest are of older age.

↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes

↳

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

Notes: Depending on a typical ceremony, adherent are asked not to practice hygiene for a long period of time until after the ceremony.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: However in some few cases where nuns are required to spend time in convents, they abstain from having. Once, they come out of the convents, some of them have children.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, adherents are required to abstain from sexual intercourse a number of days before they join a temple, a convent, or a shrine. Some ceremonies too require practitioner to abstain from sexual relation. The same can be said about Vodun priest requiring their adherents to abstain from sexual intercourse with their legitimate partners some days of the week.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Notes: In some cases, adherents are required to abstain from sexual intercourse a number of

days before they join a temple, a convent, or a shrine. Some ceremonies too require practitioner to abstain from sexual relation. The same can be said about Vodun priest requiring their adherents to abstain from sexual intercourse with their legitimate partners some days of the week.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Before participating in some ceremonies, adherents are required to fast. Others are required to fast because they believe fasting gives to the the person who does it.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: There are different food taboo depending on the tribe. The food taboo is usually related to the tribal survival history or to their ancestry. Vodun, being the divinity, reinforces the taboos.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: In contemporary West Africa Vodun, permanent scarring and bodily alterations are less and less performed. However, permanent scarring are seen on the faces of the older generation. Some of these scarification are tribal specific and allow the person to be identified to a particular tribe.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Notes: The one notable painful position is that it is not rare to see naked nuns walking and wondering in public to fulfill some of the Vodun ceremonial requirements. In some cases, they are only require to cover their sex. The ages of those naked nuns varies including children and older women.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, members are required to give away their belongings because the gods have demanded so.

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: In a case where justice is rendered by the thunder god Hebieso, the family of the dead is required not to touch any belongings of the later. All these belongings are then collected and given to the Vodun temple, convent, or shrine.

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The most observable sacrifice of time is those which lasts weeks. Adherents are convened to either weekly, monthly, or yearly ceremonies that take days and where members have to cease any activity to participate.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the initiation ceremonies include risk taking where adherents have to spend time in solitude performing dangerous activities. Due to modernity however, these physical risk taking activities are less and less performed.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Due to the alleged European demonization of this religion, members appear to be marginalized as worshipers of the devil by Christians and Muslims.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Each family tends to have their own small shrine or idol in their houses where small scale rituals are performed.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 3

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 1000

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 168

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Synchronic activities are usually seen in public ceremonies. They are usually

choreographic dances and most of the time performed by women.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Alcohol is profusely used. No matter the ceremony, rituals or event, alcohol is drunk. Alcohol is also poured on idols representing the gods.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Followers of Vodun, whether they are men or women, always have to shave their head before most of the ceremonies. This is a distinctive sign of the priests and nuns.
<https://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae6acc04.html>

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Vodun followers especially the priests and nuns are always dressed half naked living their chest uncovered and bare footed. In some cases, young women are provided with a clothe to cover their breast as shown in this photo:

<https://previews.agefotostock.com/previewimage/medibigoff/9c4d4c74e3c752d475cb08a9f6683edc/z82538556.jpg>

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: Bead jewelry are used as ornament especially for women to embellish themselves during ritual ceremonies as shown in this photo:

<https://previews.agefotostock.com/previewimage/medibigoff/8e9428b82e19a4608c224fa1b3e48c58/l22700825.jpg>

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A group of tribes.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Ewe and Fon are now scattered among five states. Each of these states provides famine relief to the religious group.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Ewe and Fon are now scattered among five states. Each of these states provides famine relief to the religious group.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: By tradition instituted by the traditional religion, the elderly and the infirm live with their families who care for them until their death.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Each state where the religious group can be found provides formal education.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Extra religious education is opened to both males and females leading to conversion to Islam and Christianity.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The formal bureaucracy within the group is the local chieftancy which is well organized and sometimes provides birth certificates, marriage certificates. They sometimes settles disputes about any issues and the state only intervenes when it becomes difficult for these chieftancies to solve these issues.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group adherents interact with the state bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The respective states where the religious groups can be found provide public food storage.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The respective states where the religious groups can be found provide water management.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The respective states where the religious groups can be found provide transportation infrastructure.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The respective states levy taxes on the members of the religious group.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The states where the religious groups can be found provide police force.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: However the process starts with the traditional judicial system. If it does not work, members refer to the state judicial system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Only the states where the religious group can be found has the monopoly of this punishment.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Only the states where the religious group can be found has the monopoly of this punishment.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The group legal code is based on ancestral practices and does not have any written formal code.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Only the states where the religious group can be found provide legal code to the adherents of the religious group.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Group adherents participate in the state's military institutions.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: European missionaries transformed the spoken Ewe and Fon languages into written languages.

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: French is spoken and written in Togo and Benin and English in Ghana.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: French is spoken and written in Togo and Benin and English in Ghana.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: Gregorian calendar is currently used by the religious group. However precolonial adherents of the religious group used the moon and marked days to mark the time and define their calendar

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Due to European colonization, the Gregorian calendar is the formal calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: They provide food for themselves through farming and through food purchase.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Food is provided through trade with the rest of the world.

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Patoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

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